

Do Homomorphic Encryption Libraries Leak When Switching Keys?

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Abstract. Security proofs for RLWE-based homomorphic encryption require fresh, independent, and uniform evaluation-key masks, but this assumption is rarely tested against real library outputs. We present GaloisProbe, a reproducible key-only audit framework that formalizes this check as a statistical distinguishing problem on the mask component sk_{k_1} and instantiates five calibrated distinguishers for collisions, linear dependence, covariance structure, regression dependence, and coefficient bias. To our knowledge, this is the first end-to-end framework that maps these proof-level assumptions to a unified, reproducible distinguisher suite for deployed HE libraries. We evaluate Microsoft SEAL 4.1.2, OpenFHE 1.4.2, and HELib 2.3.0 across four parameter settings, with three independent key generations per library and SEAL-based control injections to validate detector behavior. Within these tested settings, we observe no detectable deviation from the ideal RLWE-style randomness model: collisions and rank deficits are absent, and covariance, regression, and bias statistics stay near null expectations. The main contribution is a reusable cryptographic-auditing methodology and empirical baseline for evaluation-key randomness in deployed HE libraries.

Keywords: homomorphic encryption (HE) · Ring-LWE · key-switching keys · implementation security · randomness testing · Microsoft SEAL / OpenFHE / HELib

1 Introduction

Suppose a hospital wants a cloud provider to run analytics on patient records, but the patients' data must never be exposed to the server. Homomorphic encryption (HE) makes this possible. The data owner encrypts the data, sends it to the server, and the server computes directly on the encrypted data (addition, multiplication, and complex functions) without decryption. The result is sent back to the data owner, who decrypts it and obtains the same outcome as computation on the original plaintext. The two widely deployed schemes are BGV [6] for exact integer computation and CKKS [10] for approximate real computation, both relying on the hardness of Ring Learning with Errors (Ring-LWE) [21].

A key practical constraint is that the server cannot perform multiplications and rotations on ciphertexts alone. It requires auxiliary cryptographic objects,

called *evaluation keys*, generated by the data owner from the secret key and sent with the ciphertexts. There are two types: *relinearization keys* for multiplications and *Galois keys* (also called rotation keys) for rotations. These evaluation keys are transmitted to the server, which can read them in full.

As evaluation keys are derived from the secret key, their internal structure is critical for security. The security proof relies on the fact that all random elements within these keys are independently and uniformly distributed. However, libraries like Microsoft SEAL [25], OpenFHE [4], and HELib [16] optimize key generation significantly for performance. Concretely, three optimization strategies could inadvertently introduce structure: (i) *shared PRNG state*, if a library uses a single pseudorandom number generator whose state is advanced across all blocks in one call, a re-seeding fault or state rollback could cause two blocks to share the same mask; (ii) *NTT caching*, caching the NTT evaluation of a polynomial for reuse in multiple blocks could introduce exact or approximate repetition; and (iii) *entropy pool reuse*, drawing coefficients from a common entropy pool with insufficient mixing can introduce low-order bit biases. We call any resulting regularity *correlation leakage*. The problem we investigate is: **does any of this actually occur in real, correctly configured libraries?**

Other studies have investigated HE implementation security from different fronts. Peng [24] demonstrated attacks from parameter misuse. Aydin and Aysu [3] showed that NTT-based key generation on ARM Cortex-M4F yields the secret key from a single profiling power/EM trace, a physical side-channel attack distinct from the passive key-observation setting we consider here. Broader surveys [14, 18] catalogue cryptographic misuse in software, and Bossuat et al. [5] published IACR security guidelines for HE implementations. However, none of them tests whether key material, as produced by a correctly configured library, deviates statistically from what the theory requires. This is the gap we address.

To answer this, we built GaloisProbe, an open-source pipeline that applies five statistical tests to sk_1 blocks extracted per RNS prime (described in Section 5), and released it at <https://github.com/Ash-OblivionKey/GaloisProbe>. We apply it across four parameter settings and three independent key generations per library, and report the statistical outcomes in Section 7.

Our contributions are:

- (i) **A formalized key-only audit setting.** We model evaluation-key randomness checking as a key-indistinguishability problem over per-prime sk_1 vectors, with explicit deviation conditions (mask reuse, linear dependence, block correlation, and coefficient bias) that map implementation behavior to RLWE-assumption violations.
- (ii) **A validated distinguisher framework.** We provide five complementary distinguishers with explicit null expectations, decision criteria, multiple-testing treatment, threshold calibration, and control validation, yielding a reusable methodology for implementation-level cryptographic audits.
- (iii) **A cross-library empirical baseline.** Across SEAL 4.1.2, OpenFHE 1.4.2, and HELib 2.3.0 under four parameter settings, we observe no detectable

deviation from the ideal RLWE randomness model within tested settings, establishing a reproducible baseline for future comparative audits.

Cryptology contribution. This paper does not claim a new key-recovery attack. Its contribution is a cryptographic auditing methodology: it operationalizes proof-level randomness assumptions into concrete distinguishers with measurable detection guarantees, and demonstrates how to evaluate deployed HE implementations against those assumptions in a reproducible, key-only setting.

Main claim. The paper makes three bounded claims: (1) under the key-only threat model in Section 4, the five distinguishers in Section 5 provide a concrete and reproducible test of evaluation-key randomness assumptions; (2) in our SEAL control experiments, injected structure is detected for the targeted deviation classes; and (3) within the tested settings in Section 6, no targeted deviation is detected in SEAL, OpenFHE, or HELib outputs. These are methodological and empirical claims within study scope, not a universal proof of implementation security.

Section 2 provides background on RLWE, evaluation keys, and notation. Section 3 situates the work in the prior literature. Section 4 formalizes the adversary model and the four deviation conditions. Section 5 describes the five distinguishers, their null expectations, power analysis, control procedures, and the statistical framework. Section 6 and Section 7 detail the experimental setup and results. Section 8 and Section 9 discuss limitations and conclusions.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 How Homomorphic Encryption Works

HE processing involves three main stages. The data owner converts plaintext data into polynomial form, encrypts it with a secret key to produce ciphertexts, and uploads those ciphertexts to a server. The server performs arithmetic operations (addition and multiplication) on the ciphertexts. The data owner decrypts the result, obtaining the same outcome as computation on the original plaintext. The server never learns the plaintext at any stage.

The security of all modern HE schemes rests on the hardness of *Ring Learning with Errors* (Ring-LWE) [21]. For any party without the secret key, an RLWE ciphertext is computationally indistinguishable from uniform noise. The ring $R_q = \mathbb{Z}_q[X]/(X^N + 1)$ consists of polynomials of degree less than N with coefficients in \mathbb{Z}_q . An RLWE sample is a pair $(a, b) \in R_q^2$, where $a \leftarrow R_q$ is uniform, $s \in R_q$ is the secret key, and $e \leftarrow \chi$ is a *small* error drawn from a discrete Gaussian distribution $\chi = D_{\mathbb{Z}, \sigma}$ with width parameter $\sigma \ll q$ (so error coefficients remain small relative to the modulus). All arithmetic is in R_q , so coefficients are automatically reduced modulo q and polynomials modulo $X^N + 1$:

$$b = as + e \quad \text{in } R_q. \tag{1}$$

The *decision-RLWE assumption* states that no efficient adversary can distinguish the distribution $\{(a, as+e)\}$ from uniform over R_q^2 with non-negligible advantage.

In coefficient form, a corresponds to N coefficients each independently uniform over \mathbb{Z}_q .

2.2 Evaluation Keys and Key-Switching

The server requires evaluation keys to perform multiplications and rotations. A homomorphic multiplication of two ciphertexts under secret key s produces a result encrypted under s^2 . *Relinearization keys* allow the server to convert this back to a ciphertext under s [6]. Similarly, *Galois keys* (rotation keys) enable the server to rotate encrypted slot vectors by connecting $\pi(s)$ to s via ring automorphisms π [15]. Chase et al. [8] establish that the internal structure of these keys must match the security proof assumptions.

Each evaluation key is organized as a collection of *blocks*; each block stores one pair $(\text{ksk}_0, \text{ksk}_1)$. For each block, a is sampled uniformly from R_q and a small error e is drawn from χ :

$$\text{ksk}_1 = a, \quad \text{ksk}_0 = -s \cdot a + e + \text{key_material} \bmod q, \quad (2)$$

where key_material encodes the link between the old and new secret keys: a gadget decomposition of s^2 for relinearization keys, or $\pi(s)$ for Galois keys. The first component ksk_0 depends on the secret key, so structured behavior there is expected. The second component $\text{ksk}_1 = a$ is the fresh uniform mask and must be sampled independently for every block.

This freshness requirement is critical. Mono and Güneysu [22] emphasize that each key-switching step must use independent randomness. If two blocks share the same mask, an observer holding both ksk_1 vectors can detect the collision directly. If the vectors are linearly dependent or their coefficients are biased, the implementation deviates from the ideal model. We focus on ksk_1 because any such deviation (collision, rank deficit, covariance pattern, or coefficient bias) indicates that the library’s key generation falls outside the scope of the security proof.

2.3 Notation

Throughout the paper, N denotes the polynomial ring dimension (number of coefficients per polynomial) and L the number of RNS prime limbs. The ciphertext modulus is the product of L pairwise coprime primes:

$$q = \prod_{l=0}^{L-1} q_l, \quad \gcd(q_l, q_{l'}) = 1 \text{ for } l \neq l'. \quad (3)$$

By the Chinese Remainder Theorem, every polynomial $a \in R_q$ decomposes into L residue polynomials $a_l = a \bmod q_l \in R_{q_l}$, one per prime. A *level* in leveled HE refers to the number of remaining multiplicative operations a ciphertext supports; each homomorphic multiplication consumes one level by reducing the modulus from q by one prime factor. A *key block* is a single pair $(\text{ksk}_0, \text{ksk}_1)$

associated with one RNS prime index l and one key level. Relinearization keys contribute one block per prime per level; rotation keys add one block per automorphism per prime per level. The variable n denotes the total number of ksk_1 blocks in the dump; $n_{\text{vec}} = n/L$ denotes the block count per RNS prime. SEAL and OpenFHE store coefficients as unsigned 64-bit integers in $\{0, \dots, q_l - 1\}$; HElib uses signed 64-bit integers in $[-(q_l - 1)/2, (q_l - 1)/2]$. Our tests handle both representations.

Symbol summary. n_{cov} is the number of blocks used in covariance profiling per prime, with $n_{\text{cov}} \leq n_{\text{vec}}$. When needed, $m_l = N \cdot n_{\text{vec}}$ denotes the number of pooled coefficients at prime l .

Ideal model. Since all distinguishers operate per RNS prime, we state the ideal model in the per-prime representation. The security proofs require that each block j , for each prime l , has a coefficient vector $\mathbf{v}_j^{(l)} \in \mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^N$ drawn uniformly, $\mathbf{v}_j^{(l)} \sim \text{Uniform}(\mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^N)$, independent of every other block. Every coefficient $v_{j,i}^{(l)}$ should be uniform over $\{0, 1, \dots, q_l - 1\}$ with no correlations across blocks or positions. A deviation from this ideal occurs when two blocks coincide ($\mathbf{v}_j^{(l)} = \mathbf{v}_{j'}^{(l)}$ for $j \neq j'$), when a nontrivial linear relation holds ($\sum_j \lambda_j \mathbf{v}_j^{(l)} = \mathbf{0}$ over \mathbb{Z}_{q_l}), or when the coefficient distribution deviates from uniform (non-zero skewness, anomalous kurtosis, or low-bit bias).

For notational brevity, we drop the superscript (l) when context is clear and write \mathbf{v}_j for the coefficient vector of the j -th ksk_1 block at a fixed prime.

3 Related Work

Four strands of prior work are relevant here.

3.1 HE Implementation Security

The majority of research into HE implementation security focuses on parameter misuse [18, 24] and physical side channels [3]. Peng [24] demonstrated that attackers could exploit SEAL by misusing parameters, concluding that “FHE is extremely dangerous to use without a crypto expert.” Aydin and Aysu [3] showed that NTT-based key generation on ARM Cortex-M4F requires only a single profiling power/EM trace to recover the secret key with >98% accuracy. Egele et al. [14] and Lazar et al. [18] surveyed cryptographic misuse in software more broadly, and Bossuat et al. [5] published IACR security guidelines for HE implementations. Our setting is different: we do not assume physical access, a decryption oracle, or misconfigured parameters. Instead, we consider the complementary key-only passive setting, where only evaluation-key material is observed and tested for statistical deviations from the ideal model.

3.2 RLWE and LWE Cryptanalysis

Classical RLWE cryptanalysis proceeds against the search or decision problem when attackers possess many samples [7, 9]. Chen et al. [9] used subfield structure and χ^2 testing to attack search-RLWE with small error. Castryck et al. [7]

identified the weakest provably vulnerable RLWE instances. Both approaches require many samples to recover the secret key or to distinguish from uniform. Our situation is different: we have a fixed, finite collection of evaluation-key blocks (hundreds to a few thousand), no distinguishing oracle, and no ciphertexts. The patterns we investigate (mask reuse, rank deficiency, coefficient bias) are *implementation-induced* regularities that would break the RLWE model even without enabling full key recovery.

3.3 Key-Switching and Evaluation Keys

The most expensive primitive in BGV and CKKS is key switching. Mono and Güneysu [22] showed that single-decomposition outperforms double-decomposition in practice, and emphasized that each key-switching operation requires fresh, independent randomness for every block. Mono et al. [23] studied how prime bit-lengths affect key-switching noise. Duong and Lee [13] developed pipelined hardware accelerators for CKKS key switching. Chase et al. [8] formalize security requirements for switching-key structures, including assumptions on correctly distributed randomness. The Homomorphic Encryption Standard [2] defines structural requirements and parameter specifications. Existing work covers correctness, speed, and parameter selection, but does not verify whether actual library output matches the statistical profile required by theory.

3.4 Statistical Randomness Testing and Correlation Attacks

Our distinguishers draw on two separate traditions. On the **randomness-testing** side, Luengo and Villalba [20] recommend comprehensive test batteries for cryptographic output, and Demirhan and Bitirim [12] implemented such tests in the CryptRndTest R package. From these we adapted hash-based collision detection, rank computation over finite fields, and moment-based bias checks; null expectations (e.g., excess kurtosis ≈ -1.2 for uniform mod q_l) are well-known results [17]. On the **correlation-attack** side, Vaudenay [26] provided a statistical framework for linear and differential cryptanalysis and demonstrated χ^2 cryptanalysis on DES, while Lu et al. [19] extended conditional-correlation techniques to break Bluetooth E0. We apply the same principles to evaluation-key blocks under a null hypothesis of independence and uniformity rather than to a specific cipher construction.

4 Adversary Model and Threat

We model the adversary as the untrusted cloud evaluator in a *key-only passive* setting: the adversary receives the evaluation keys but has no decryption oracle, no ciphertexts, and no side-channel access. This is a key-indistinguishability experiment, strictly weaker than the standard IND-CPA model (which also gives the adversary a ciphertext oracle), and represents the minimal requirement: if even this passive observer can distinguish key material from uniform random,

the library’s key generation violates the ideal model. The adversary’s only input is the collection of per-prime sk_1 coefficient vectors.

Adversary’s view. For each RNS prime $l \in \{0, \dots, L - 1\}$, the adversary observes the n_{vec} mask vectors

$$\mathcal{V}^{(l)} = \{\mathbf{v}_1^{(l)}, \mathbf{v}_2^{(l)}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{n_{\text{vec}}}^{(l)}\}, \quad \mathbf{v}_j^{(l)} \in \mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^N, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_j^{(l)}$ is the coefficient vector of sk_1 for the j -th block at prime l . The secret-dependent rows sk_0 are not required; the adversary works with $\mathcal{V}^{(l)}$ alone for each prime. We write $\mathcal{V} = \bigcup_l \mathcal{V}^{(l)}$ for the full collection.

Ideal distribution. Under the RLWE assumption [21], each block must be an independent, uniform draw from $\mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^N$. Formally, define the ideal distribution $\mathcal{D}_{\text{ideal}}$ by

$$\mathcal{D}_{\text{ideal}} : \quad \mathbf{v}_j^{(l)} \stackrel{\text{i.i.d.}}{\sim} \text{Uniform}(\mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^N), \quad j = 1, \dots, n_{\text{vec}}, \quad l = 0, \dots, L - 1. \quad (5)$$

Every coefficient $v_{j,i}^{(l)}$ is independently uniform over $\{0, 1, \dots, q_l - 1\}$, and blocks share no dependence within or across primes.

Real distribution. Let $\mathcal{D}_{\text{real}}$ denote the actual distribution of \mathcal{V} as produced by the library. If the implementation is correct, $\mathcal{D}_{\text{real}} = \mathcal{D}_{\text{ideal}}$.

Distinguishing advantage. A distinguisher \mathcal{A} is a (possibly randomized) algorithm that takes \mathcal{V} and outputs a bit. Its advantage is

$$\text{Adv}(\mathcal{A}) = |\Pr[\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{D}_{\text{real}}) = 1] - \Pr[\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{D}_{\text{ideal}}) = 1]|. \quad (6)$$

If $\text{Adv}(\mathcal{A})$ is non-negligible for some efficient \mathcal{A} , the implementation deviates from the ideal.

Deviation conditions. We formalize four types of deviation that our distinguishers target:

- (a) *Mask reuse.* $\exists j \neq j'$ such that $\mathbf{v}_j^{(l)} = \mathbf{v}_{j'}^{(l)}$ for some l .
- (b) *Linear dependence.* $\exists \boldsymbol{\lambda} \in \mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^{n_{\text{vec}}} \setminus \{\mathbf{0}\}$ such that $\sum_j \lambda_j \mathbf{v}_j^{(l)} = \mathbf{0}$ over \mathbb{Z}_{q_l} for some l .
- (c) *Correlation.* For some pair (j, j') with $j \neq j'$, the empirical covariance $\text{Cov}(\mathbf{v}_j^{(l)}, \mathbf{v}_{j'}^{(l)})$ or the regression coefficient $R^2(\mathbf{v}_j^{(l)}, \mathbf{v}_{j'}^{(l)})$ deviates significantly from the null.
- (d) *Coefficient bias.* The marginal distribution of $v_{j,i}^{(l)}$ deviates from $\text{Uniform}(\mathbb{Z}_{q_l})$, detected via low-bit mean $\neq 1/2$, skewness $\neq 0$, or excess kurtosis $\neq -6/5$.

Bossuat et al. [5] emphasize that “the implementation needs to conform to this ideal model.” If any of (a) through (d) holds, the implementation falls outside the scope of the security proof. Table 1 summarizes the ideal properties and their deviations. Note that detecting these deviations does not automatically imply key recovery.

Table 1. Ideal vs. potential deviant structure in ksk_1 (per RNS prime).

Aspect	Ideal	Deviant
Randomness	Fresh per block	Mask reuse
Linear independence	Full rank over \mathbb{Z}_{q_l}	Rank deficiency
Covariance	\approx diagonal (scaled by σ_l^2)	Off-diagonal structure
Coefficients	Uniform mod q_l	Low-bit bias, skewness, kurtosis

5 Methodology

5.1 Pipeline Overview

GaloisProbe has four stages: (1) key generation and dumping, (2) schema verification, (3) distinguisher analysis, and (4) reporting.

In the first stage, C++ instrumentation tools link against each HE library (SEAL, OpenFHE, HELib), generate keys with fixed parameters, and write every ksk_0 and ksk_1 polynomial to a shared schema: a `metadata.json` file plus `relin/` and `rotation/` subdirectories of `.bin` files, each storing N coefficients at 8 bytes (little-endian) per RNS prime, following the HE Standard [2]. The second stage checks that metadata is internally consistent (block count, coefficient size, prime list). The third stage runs all five distinguishers on the ksk_1 blocks. The fourth stage collects outputs and computes p-values and z-scores.

SEAL stores coefficients in NTT (Number Theoretic Transform) form. The NTT maps $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^N$ to $\hat{\mathbf{c}} \in \mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^N$ via

$$\hat{c}_k = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} c_i \omega^{ik} \pmod{q_l}, \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1, \quad (7)$$

for $\omega \in \mathbb{Z}_{q_l}$ a primitive $2N$ -th root of unity (i.e., $\omega^{2N} \equiv 1$ and $\omega^N \equiv -1 \pmod{q_l}$). Such ω exists if and only if $q_l \equiv 1 \pmod{2N}$; SEAL’s RNS primes are specifically chosen to satisfy this condition. Because NTT is a bijection on $\mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^N$, uniformity is preserved: $\mathbf{c} \sim \text{Uniform}(\mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^N) \Rightarrow \hat{\mathbf{c}} \sim \text{Uniform}(\mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^N)$. We analyze SEAL’s NTT-domain coefficients directly, without inverting the transform. Furthermore, because NTT is applied independently and identically to each block, this block-wise linear bijection cannot introduce cross-block correlations absent in the original domain, nor remove existing ones; inter-block independence is preserved. The positive control (Section 5.4) confirms that injected structure remains detectable in this domain.

5.2 Distinguishers

The test suite is built on a single principle: if key generation is correct, the ksk_1 blocks should be indistinguishable from independent draws from a uniform distribution. Each of the five tests below probes a different failure mode (duplicate blocks, exact linear dependencies, correlated fluctuations, pairwise predictability, or biased values), and together they cover all four deviation conditions from

Section 4. Each test implicitly defines a distinguisher \mathcal{A} : \mathcal{A} outputs 1 if and only if the test rejects, so a rejection implies $\text{Adv}(\mathcal{A}) > 0$. Every subsection specifies what the test detects, the procedure, the null expectation, and the rejection rule.

Distinguisher A: Shared-Mask Collision If the library accidentally reuses the same random mask for two key blocks, those blocks will be identical. This test fingerprints every block and checks for matching fingerprints.

Detects: mask reuse (deviation condition (a)).

Procedure. Compute a SHA-256 hash of each ksk_1 coefficient vector: $h_j = \text{SHA256}(\mathbf{v}_j)$ for $j = 1, \dots, n$. Count the number of pairs (j, j') with $j \neq j'$ and $h_j = h_{j'}$.

Null. Under $\mathcal{D}_{\text{ideal}}$, the input blocks are independent. Modeling SHA-256 as a random oracle (standard in hash-based collision analysis), the output hashes are independent and uniform over $\{0, 1\}^{256}$. By the union bound over the $\binom{n}{2}$ pairs:

$$\Pr(\text{at least one collision}) \leq \frac{n(n-1)}{2 \cdot 2^{256}} \leq \frac{n^2}{2 \cdot 2^{256}}. \quad (8)$$

For $n \leq 12,312$ (our largest dump), $\Pr(\text{collision}) < 10^{-69}$ [20].

Decision. Any collision (`collision_count` ≥ 1) rejects the null.

Distinguisher B: Rank Deficiency Under the ideal model, independently sampled uniform vectors over $\mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^N$ are in general position: stacking them into a matrix yields full rank. A rank deficit means at least one block is an exact linear combination of the others over \mathbb{Z}_{q_l} , which cannot occur by chance with non-negligible probability.

Detects: linear dependence (deviation condition (b)).

Procedure. For each RNS prime l , stack the n_{vec} coefficient vectors as rows of $M \in \mathbb{Z}_{q_l}^{n_{\text{vec}} \times N}$ and compute its rank by Gaussian elimination over \mathbb{Z}_{q_l} (since q_l is prime, exact arithmetic is used throughout, implemented via Python arbitrary-precision integers). Define

$$\text{deficit} = n_{\text{vec}} - \text{rank}(M). \quad (9)$$

Null. Under $\mathcal{D}_{\text{ideal}}$, M has full rank with overwhelming probability. The formal bound from Section 5.5 is $\Pr(\text{deficit} > 0) \leq n_{\text{vec}}/q_l^{N-n_{\text{vec}}+1}$. For the standard SEAL configuration ($n_{\text{vec}} = 46$, $N = 4096$, $q_l \approx 2^{36}$), this is below 10^{-43000} .

Decision. `deficit` > 0 for any tested prime rejects the null. In configurations where all rows are tested (SEAL, OpenFHE), this is equivalent to testing all blocks for that prime; for HELib we use the sampling protocol described in Section 5.7 and Section 8.

Distinguisher C: Covariance Profiling Independent blocks have no systematic relationship between their coefficient values at any shared position. This test measures how much energy sits in the off-diagonal entries of the empirical block

covariance matrix C ; under independence, those entries are mean-zero noise and the off-diagonal ratio ρ stays near its null expectation.

Detects: pairwise block-level correlation (deviation condition (c)).

Procedure. For each RNS prime, arrange the first n_{cov} coefficient vectors as *columns* of $X \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times n_{\text{cov}}}$ (so each of the N coefficient positions is a row observation), center each column to zero mean, and compute the empirical block covariance:

$$C = \frac{1}{N-1} X^\top X \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\text{cov}} \times n_{\text{cov}}}, \quad C_{jj'} = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (X_{ij} - \bar{X}_j)(X_{ij'} - \bar{X}_{j'}). \quad (10)$$

The test statistic is the *off-diagonal ratio*, where $\text{diag}(C)$ denotes the diagonal matrix formed by zeroing all off-diagonal entries of C :

$$\rho = \frac{\|C - \text{diag}(C)\|_F}{\|\text{diag}(C)\|_F} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j \neq j'} C_{jj'}^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_j C_{jj}^2}}. \quad (11)$$

We also report $\|C\|_F$ for reference. We set $n_{\text{cov}} = \min(n_{\text{vec}}, \lfloor 1 + 0.01(N-1) \rfloor)$ to keep $\rho_{\text{null}} \lesssim 0.10$. This bound follows from inverting the null formula: $\rho_{\text{null}} \leq 0.10$ requires $\sqrt{(n_{\text{cov}} - 1)/(N - 1)} \leq 0.10$, i.e. $n_{\text{cov}} \leq 1 + 0.01(N - 1)$. The floor term is 41 for SEAL ($N = 4096$), 164 for OpenFHE ($N = 16384$), and 21 for HELib ($N = 2048$); since $n_{\text{vec}} = 42 < 164$ for OpenFHE, all blocks are used there. This gives $n_{\text{cov}} = 41$ for SEAL (main), $n_{\text{cov}} = 23$ for SEAL (stress, $N = 32768$; limited by $n_{\text{vec}} = 23$), $n_{\text{cov}} = 42$ for OpenFHE, and $n_{\text{cov}} = 21$ for HELib.

Null. Under $\mathcal{D}_{\text{ideal}}$, the population block covariance is diagonal:

$$C^* = \sigma_l^2 I_{n_{\text{cov}}}, \quad \sigma_l^2 = \frac{q_l^2 - 1}{12}. \quad (12)$$

Each off-diagonal entry $C_{jj'}$ ($j \neq j'$) has mean 0 and, by the CLT over N coefficient observations, variance $\approx \sigma_l^4/(N-1)$. The $n_{\text{cov}}(n_{\text{cov}}-1)$ off-diagonal entries each contribute $\approx \sigma_l^4/(N-1)$ to $\|C - \text{diag}(C)\|_F^2$, while each diagonal C_{jj} contributes $\approx \sigma_l^4$ to $\|\text{diag}(C)\|_F^2$. Therefore:

$$\rho_{\text{null}}^2 \approx \frac{n_{\text{cov}}(n_{\text{cov}}-1) \cdot \sigma_l^4/(N-1)}{n_{\text{cov}} \cdot \sigma_l^4} = \frac{n_{\text{cov}}-1}{N-1}, \quad \rho_{\text{null}} \approx \sqrt{\frac{n_{\text{cov}}-1}{N-1}}. \quad (13)$$

For SEAL main ($n_{\text{cov}} = 41$, $N = 4096$), $\rho_{\text{null}} \approx 0.10$; for SEAL stress ($n_{\text{cov}} = 23$, $N = 32768$), ≈ 0.026 ; for OpenFHE ($n_{\text{cov}} = 42$, $N = 16384$), ≈ 0.05 ; for HELib ($n_{\text{cov}} = 21$, $N = 2048$), ≈ 0.099 . The 99th-percentile from null simulations is in Table 3.

Decision. $\rho > 0.15$ rejects the null. This threshold lies above the simulated 99th percentile for all three configurations (Table 3).

Distinguisher D: Regression Dependence A direct check for pairwise dependence: can one block be linearly predicted from another? If fitting $\mathbf{y} \approx \beta \mathbf{x}$ produces a near-perfect fit ($R^2 \rightarrow 1$), the two blocks are not independent.

Detects: pairwise linear relations between blocks (deviation condition (c)).

Procedure. For pairs (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) of ksk_1 coefficient vectors within the same RNS prime, fit the no-intercept model $y_i = \beta x_i + \varepsilon_i$ via OLS:

$$\hat{\beta} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i y_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^2} = \frac{\langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \rangle}{\|\mathbf{x}\|^2}. \quad (14)$$

The coefficient of determination uses the *centered* total sum of squares:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\text{SS}_{\text{res}}}{\text{SS}_{\text{tot}}}, \quad \text{SS}_{\text{tot}} = \sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2, \quad \text{SS}_{\text{res}} = \sum_i (y_i - \hat{\beta} x_i)^2. \quad (15)$$

Using the centered SS_{tot} with a no-intercept fit permits $R^2 < 0$, which occurs when the forced-zero-intercept model performs worse than predicting the mean. SEAL and OpenFHE test all pairs within each prime; HELib samples 500,000 pairs uniformly at random.

Null. Under $\mathcal{D}_{\text{ideal}}$, \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} are i.i.d. with mean μ and variance σ^2 . Because $\mathbf{x} \perp \mathbf{y}$, the law of large numbers gives $\hat{\beta} \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[XY]/\mathbb{E}[X^2] = \mu^2/(\mu^2 + \sigma^2)$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$. For large N , the asymptotic expected no-intercept R^2 is (the finite- N correction is $O(1/N)$, negligible for $N \geq 4096$):

$$\mathbb{E}[R^2] = -\frac{\mu^2}{\mu^2 + \sigma^2}. \quad (16)$$

Derivation. By independence, $\mathbb{E}[XY] = \mu^2$ and $\mathbb{E}[X^2] = \mu^2 + \sigma^2$. Substituting $\hat{\beta} = \mu^2/(\mu^2 + \sigma^2)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[(Y - \hat{\beta}X)^2] &= \mathbb{E}[Y^2] - 2\hat{\beta}\mathbb{E}[XY] + \hat{\beta}^2\mathbb{E}[X^2] \\ &= (\sigma^2 + \mu^2) - \frac{2\mu^4}{\mu^2 + \sigma^2} + \frac{\mu^4}{\mu^2 + \sigma^2} \\ &= \sigma^2 + \mu^2 - \frac{\mu^4}{\mu^2 + \sigma^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\text{SS}_{\text{res}} \approx N(\sigma^2 + \mu^2 - \mu^4/(\mu^2 + \sigma^2))$ and $\text{SS}_{\text{tot}} = N\sigma^2$. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} R^2 &= 1 - \frac{\sigma^2 + \mu^2 - \mu^4/(\mu^2 + \sigma^2)}{\sigma^2} \\ &= -\frac{\mu^2}{\sigma^2} + \frac{\mu^4}{\sigma^2(\mu^2 + \sigma^2)} \\ &= -\frac{\mu^2(\mu^2 + \sigma^2) - \mu^4}{\sigma^2(\mu^2 + \sigma^2)} = -\frac{\mu^2}{\mu^2 + \sigma^2}. \end{aligned}$$

For unsigned coefficients (SEAL, OpenFHE), $\mu = (q_l - 1)/2$ and $\sigma^2 = (q_l^2 - 1)/12$:

$$\mathbb{E}[R^2] = -\frac{3(q_l - 1)}{2(2q_l - 1)} \rightarrow -\frac{3}{4} = -0.75 \quad \text{as } q_l \rightarrow \infty. \quad (17)$$

For signed (centered) coefficients (HElib), $\mu \approx 0$, so $\mathbb{E}[R^2] \rightarrow 0$. Both values are consistent with independence, not leakage [26].

Decision. $R_{\max}^2 > 0.9$ across all tested pairs rejects the null. We report `r2_mean` and `r2_max`.

Distinguisher E: Bias and Moments Even if blocks are mutually independent, the individual coefficients within each block must look uniformly random. This test checks three distributional properties: whether odd and even values appear equally (low-bit mean), whether the distribution is symmetric (skewness), and whether its shape matches the flat profile of a uniform distribution (excess kurtosis). We complement threshold decisions with formal z-scores to quantify statistical significance.

Detects: non-uniform coefficient distribution (deviation condition (d)).

Procedure. For each RNS prime l , pool all $m_l = N \cdot n_{\text{vec}}$ coefficients from the corresponding blocks and center them into $(-q_l/2, q_l/2]$. For the low-bit statistic, parity is computed on the canonical residue class in $\{0, \dots, q_l - 1\}$ (equivalently, after reducing centered values mod q_l). Compute three statistics.

Low-bit mean (fraction of odd coefficients) and its z-score: each coefficient $c_i \bmod 2$ is a Bernoulli trial with parameter $p = 1/2$ under the null, so the sample mean lowbit_l has standard error $1/(2\sqrt{m_l})$ by the CLT. By the CLT, $(\text{lowbit}_l - 1/2) \cdot 2\sqrt{m_l} \approx \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$; taking absolute value gives a half-normal statistic:

$$\text{lowbit}_l = \frac{1}{m_l} \sum_{i=1}^{m_l} (c_i \bmod 2), \quad z_l^{\text{lb}} = |\text{lowbit}_l - \frac{1}{2}| \cdot 2\sqrt{m_l} \stackrel{H_0}{\sim} \text{HalfNormal}(0, 1). \quad (18)$$

A two-sided p-value $< 10^{-3}$ corresponds to $z_l^{\text{lb}} > 3.29$ (since $2\Phi(-3.29) \approx 10^{-3}$ for the standard normal).

Skewness and *excess kurtosis* (biased estimators; for our sample sizes $m_l \geq 188,416$ the bias is negligible):

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{1}{m_l} \sum_{i=1}^{m_l} \left(\frac{c_i - \bar{c}}{\hat{\sigma}} \right)^3, \quad \kappa = \frac{1}{m_l} \sum_{i=1}^{m_l} \left(\frac{c_i - \bar{c}}{\hat{\sigma}} \right)^4 - 3, \quad (19)$$

where $\bar{c} = m_l^{-1} \sum_i c_i$ and $\hat{\sigma}^2 = m_l^{-1} \sum_i (c_i - \bar{c})^2$.

Null. For discrete uniform over $\{0, \dots, q_l - 1\}$:

- $\Pr(c \equiv 1 \bmod 2) = (q_l - 1)/(2q_l)$ for odd q_l , so $\Pr(c \equiv 1 \bmod 2) = 1/2 - 1/(2q_l) \rightarrow 1/2$ as q_l grows.
- $\gamma_1 = 0$ by symmetry of the uniform distribution about its mean.
- $\kappa = -6/5 = -1.2$ [17].

The kurtosis result follows from the population moments of $\text{Uniform}\{0, \dots, q_l - 1\}$ (where μ denotes the mean and μ_4 the 4th central moment):

$$\mu = \frac{q_l - 1}{2}, \quad \sigma^2 = \frac{q_l^2 - 1}{12}, \quad \mu_4 = \frac{(q_l^2 - 1)(3q_l^2 - 7)}{240}, \quad (20)$$

Table 2. Null expectations and decision criteria for each distinguisher.

Distinguisher	Null expectation	Reject if
Collision	0 collisions	≥ 1 collision
Rank	deficit = 0	deficit > 0
Covariance	$\rho \approx \sqrt{(n_{\text{cov}} - 1)/(N - 1)}$	$\rho > 0.15$
Regression	$R^2 \approx -0.75$ (SEAL, OpenFHE) or ≈ 0 (HElib)	$R_{\text{max}}^2 > 0.9$
Bias	lowbit ≈ 0.5 , $z^{\text{lb}} \lesssim 3$, $\gamma_1 \approx 0$, $\kappa \approx -1.2$	$z^{\text{lb}} > 3.29$, $ \gamma_1 > 0.1$, or $\kappa \notin [-1.4, -1.0]$

giving $\kappa = \mu_4/\sigma^4 - 3 = -6(q_l^2 + 1)/(5(q_l^2 - 1)) \rightarrow -6/5$ as $q_l \rightarrow \infty$, where $\sigma^4 = (q_l^2 - 1)^2/144$.

Decision. Formal: $z_l^{\text{lb}} > 3.29$ (two-sided $p < 10^{-3}$) rejects the null for low-bit bias. Threshold-based: lowbit $\notin [0.48, 0.52]$, $|\gamma_1| > 0.1$, or $\kappa \notin [-1.4, -1.0]$ also rejects. All metrics are reported per prime and aggregated.

5.3 Summary of Null Expectations

Table 2 consolidates the null expectation and decision criterion for each distinguisher.

5.4 Control Procedures

Each distinguisher is validated by three control experiments confirming it detects known structure and stays silent on clean data. These controls were executed on SEAL only.

- (1) **Positive control.** One ksk_1 block is duplicated verbatim. Expected: `collision_count` = 1, deficit ≥ 1 .
- (2) **Scaled control.** In a reduced dump (7 blocks), one block is replaced by $\mathbf{v}_{j'} = \lambda \mathbf{v}_j \bmod q_l$ for a known scalar $\lambda \in \mathbb{Z}_{q_l} \setminus \{0, 1\}$ (so that the scaled block is neither the zero vector nor a duplicate). Expected: deficit ≥ 1 , elevated ρ ; collision stays 0 (scaled block hashes differently from \mathbf{v}_j).
- (3) **Fresh control.** Three fully independent key dumps are generated. Expected: 0 collisions, 0 deficit, $R^2 \approx -0.75$ or near 0, lowbit ≈ 0.5 , and no false alarms.

5.5 Statistical Framework

Collision p -value. For $c = 0$, $p_{\text{coll}} = 1$. For $c \geq 1$, the birthday bound gives $p_{\text{coll}} \leq n^2/(2 \cdot 2^{256})$, negligible for our block counts; we set $p_{\text{coll}} \approx 0$.

Rank p -value. For r rows drawn i.i.d. uniform from $\mathbb{Z}_{q_i}^N$ with q_i prime and $r \leq N$, the matrix $M \in \mathbb{Z}_{q_i}^{r \times N}$ has full rank with probability at least $1 - r q_i^{-(N-r+1)}$. In our experiments, $r = n_{\text{vec}}$ for SEAL/OpenFHE and $r = 500$ for HELib (row cap).

Proof. Let $\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_r$ be the rows. After conditioning on $\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_{i-1}$, their span has dimension at most $i-1$, containing q_i^{i-1} elements out of q_i^N total. A uniformly random $\mathbf{r}_i \in \mathbb{Z}_{q_i}^N$ lies in this subspace with probability $q_i^{i-1}/q_i^N = q_i^{i-1-N}$. Summing over all r rows by the union bound:

$$\Pr(\text{rank}(M) < r) \leq \sum_{i=1}^r q_i^{i-1-N}. \quad (21)$$

Since each term q_i^{i-1-N} is maximized at $i = r$ (giving q_i^{r-1-N}), and there are r terms, the sum is bounded by $r \cdot q_i^{r-1-N} = r/q_i^{N-r+1}$.

For the standard SEAL configuration ($n_{\text{vec}} = 46$, $N = 4096$, $q_i \approx 2^{36}$), the exponent is $36 \times (4096 - 46 + 1) = 36 \times 4051 = 145,836$, giving a bound of $46/2^{145836} < 10^{-43000}$ (using $\log_{10}(2^{145836}) \approx 43,898$). We set $p_{\text{rank}} = 1$ when deficit = 0 and $p_{\text{rank}} \approx 0$ when deficit > 0.

Bonferroni correction. With k simultaneous tests at family-wise level δ , we reject only when $\min_i p_i \leq \delta/k$. By the union bound, $\Pr(\text{any false rejection}) \leq k \cdot (\delta/k) = \delta$ [20]. In our setting, the five test families decompose into per-prime and global subtests: collision produces 1 global test; rank, covariance, and regression each produce L per-prime tests; and bias produces L per-prime tests for each of 3 statistics (z^{lb} , γ_1 , κ). In general, $k = 1 + 6L$ (one collision test, three test families each contributing L per-prime tests, and bias contributing $3L$ per-prime tests). For SEAL main ($L = 3$), $k = 1 + 6 \times 3 = 19$; for OpenFHE ($L = 8$), $k = 1 + 6 \times 8 = 49$.

5.6 Threshold Validation

The decision thresholds in Table 2 were calibrated against 100 independent draws of ideal uniform blocks for three configurations: SEAL-like ($n_{\text{vec}} = 46$, $N = 4096$), OpenFHE-like ($n_{\text{vec}} = 42$, $N = 16384$), and HELib-like ($n_{\text{vec}} = 2052$, $N = 2048$). For collision, the corresponding total block counts are $n = L \cdot n_{\text{vec}}$, i.e., 138, 336, and 12,312 respectively; using smaller n gives a broader null and therefore conservative collision thresholds at larger n . For covariance, regression, and bias, calibration and experiment use the same per-prime block counts n_{vec} ; for rank, HELib uses the row-capped protocol ($r = 500$) described in Section 5.5 and Section 5.7.

Table 3 gives the 99th percentiles. Every threshold lies well outside these empirical percentiles.

Table 3. 99th percentiles under null (100 simulations per config). ρ uses the $N \times n_{\text{cov}}$ orientation with $n_{\text{cov}} = 41, 42, 21$ for SEAL-, OpenFHE-, HELib-like respectively.

Config	Metric	99th pctl
SEAL-like	$ \text{lowbit} - 0.5 $	0.0029
	$z_{\text{max}}^{\text{lb}}$	2.51
	$ \gamma_1 $ (skewness)	0.0090
	$ \kappa + 1.2 $ (kurtosis)	0.0056
	R_{max}^2	-0.62
	ρ	0.104
OpenFHE-like	$ \text{lowbit} - 0.5 $	0.0014
	$z_{\text{max}}^{\text{lb}}$	2.03
	$ \gamma_1 $ (skewness)	0.0049
	$ \kappa + 1.2 $ (kurtosis)	0.0032
	R_{max}^2	-0.69
	ρ	0.053
HElib-like	$ \text{lowbit} - 0.5 $	0.0006
	$z_{\text{max}}^{\text{lb}}$	2.45
	$ \gamma_1 $ (skewness)	0.0016
	$ \kappa + 1.2 $ (kurtosis)	0.0015
	R_{max}^2	-0.55
	ρ	0.111

5.7 Power Analysis

A negative result is only meaningful if the tests have adequate power to detect realistic deviations. We characterize the minimum detectable effect for each distinguisher.

Collision. The test detects any exact mask reuse ($\mathbf{v}_j = \mathbf{v}_{j'}$ for any pair) with probability 1. It has no power against near-collisions or approximate dependence short of exact equality.

Rank. When all blocks are tested, any exact linear dependence (deficit > 0) is detected with probability 1. For HELib, rows are capped at 500 sampled uniformly from $n_{\text{vec}} = 2,052$; under this cap a single dependent block is detected with probability $500/2052 \approx 0.24$. Full sensitivity requires testing all rows or repeating with multiple independent samples. The test has no power against approximate linear relations that do not reduce the rank of M over \mathbb{Z}_{q_l} .

Bias. The number of pooled coefficients for prime l is $m_l = N \cdot n_{\text{vec}}$. The null distribution of lowbit_l has standard deviation $\sigma_p = 1/(2\sqrt{m_l})$. Table 4 shows the minimum detectable bias $|\Delta p| = 3.29 \sigma_p$ at a per-prime level of 10^{-3} (i.e., $z_l^{\text{lb}} > 3.29$) for each configuration. The threshold-based criterion of $|\text{lowbit} - 0.5| > 0.02$ is much more conservative and flags only large violations; the z-score criterion provides substantially finer resolution.

Covariance. The off-diagonal ratio ρ under the null has expected value $\rho_{\text{null}} \approx \sqrt{(n_{\text{cov}} - 1)/(N - 1)}$. The rejection threshold $\rho > 0.15$ lies above the simulated

Table 4. Minimum detectable low-bit bias $|\Delta p|$ at $p < 10^{-3}$ (z-score criterion), and threshold distance in units of σ_p .

Config	m_l	σ_p	$ \Delta p _{\min}$	Threshold / σ_p
SEAL (main)	188 416	0.00115	0.0038	17.4σ
SEAL (stress)	753 664	0.000576	0.0019	34.7σ
OpenFHE	688 128	0.000603	0.0020	33.2σ
HElib	4 202 496	0.000244	0.00080	82.0σ

Table 5. Time and space complexity per distinguisher.

Distinguisher	Time	Space
Collision	$O(n \cdot N)$	$O(n)$
Rank	$O(n_{\text{vec}}^2 \cdot N)$ per prime	$O(n_{\text{vec}} \cdot N)$
Covariance	$O(N \cdot n_{\text{cov}}^2)$ per prime	$O(N \cdot n_{\text{cov}})$
Regression	$O(P \cdot N)$	$O(N)$
Bias	$O(n_{\text{vec}} \cdot N)$ per prime	$O(1)^\dagger$

$^\dagger O(1)$ space holds when moments are computed incrementally (e.g. Welford’s online algorithm); naïve pooling of all m_l coefficients requires $O(n_{\text{vec}} \cdot N)$ space.

99th percentile for the three calibration configurations in Table 3 and corresponds to an off-diagonal ratio $1.5\times$ the SEAL null mean of 0.10. The test detects moderate-to-strong covariance structure; spectral analysis of C would be needed to detect subtle correlations where ρ only slightly exceeds ρ_{null} .

Regression. The threshold $R_{\text{max}}^2 > 0.9$ is intentionally stringent, designed to flag near-exact pairwise linear relations. From Table 3, the null 99th percentile for R_{max}^2 is approximately -0.55 to -0.62 , far below 0. Any R_{max}^2 substantially above 0 (e.g., > 0.1) warrants investigation even if it falls below the formal rejection threshold.

Summary. The collision test is maximally sensitive to exact mask reuse. The rank test is maximally sensitive when all blocks are tested; under the 500-row sampling cap for HElib, per-block detection probability is ≈ 0.24 . The bias test, using the z-score criterion, detects sub-percent biases ($< 0.4\%$ for SEAL, $< 0.08\%$ for HElib). The covariance and regression tests detect only moderate-to-strong structure; spectral analysis of C or non-linear regression tests would be needed to close these gaps.

5.8 Computational Complexity

Let n be the total block count, n_{vec} the blocks per prime, $n_{\text{cov}} \leq n_{\text{vec}}$ the cap for covariance, and P the number of regression pairs ($P = \binom{n_{\text{vec}}}{2}$ or 500,000 for HElib). Table 5 gives the cost per distinguisher.

Table 6. Parameter settings per library and configuration.

Library	Scheme	N	$L \approx \log_2 q_l$	Blocks	n_{vec}	
SEAL	CKKS	4096	3	36	138	46
SEAL (stress)	CKKS	32768	8	60	184	23
OpenFHE	CKKS	16384	8	50	336	42
HElib	BGV	2048	6	20	12312	2052

6 Experimental Setup

We ran GaloisProbe against three widely deployed libraries: Microsoft SEAL 4.1.2 [25], OpenFHE 1.4.2 [4], and HELib 2.3.0 [16]. The parameter settings are summarized in Table 6. SEAL and OpenFHE were tested with CKKS [10]; HELib was tested with BGV [6]. To push the pipeline to a larger ring dimension, we also ran SEAL under a stress setting at $N = 32768$.

Each library was tested with three independent key generations plus the positive, scaled, and fresh controls from Section 5. All experiments ran on a single machine: AMD Ryzen 5 4600H, 24 GB RAM, Windows 11. The C++ instrumentation was compiled with GCC 15.2.0 (MinGW/MSYS2), C++17, CMake 4.2.3. Statistical analysis used Python 3.12.10, NumPy 2.4.2, SciPy 1.17.1, and Matplotlib 3.10.8.

7 Results

7.1 Main Finding

All five distinguishers were consistent with the null model across all libraries, tested parameter settings, and independent runs. Across the three main libraries (3+8+6 RNS primes, 3 runs each), all 51 (library \times prime \times run) combinations produced zero collision counts and zero rank deficits, giving $p_{coll} = p_{rank} = 1.0$ (see Section 5.5: $p = 1$ when no violation is detected). R^2 values were negative or near zero; low-bit means were ≈ 0.5 ; kurtosis was ≈ -1.2 throughout. These results are consistent with the standard RLWE model under the tested settings.

7.2 Per-Library Results and Run Consistency

Table 7 reports the mean and [min, max] across 3 runs per library. Narrow ranges confirm per-run stability: all metrics remained within the sampling variability predicted under the null hypothesis.

The R^2 mean of -0.75 for SEAL and OpenFHE matches the theoretical expectation $\mathbb{E}[R^2] \rightarrow -3/4$ derived in Section 5.2. HELib’s $R^2 \approx 0$ matches $\mathbb{E}[R^2] \rightarrow 0$ for signed centered coefficients. The maximum R^2 across all 500k sampled pairs in HELib was 0.012, negligible. All observed ρ_{obs} values are below the rejection threshold of 0.15; for the three main-library configurations, they also lie within the empirical null band from Table 3. All z_{max}^{lb} values remained below 3, consistent with Table 3.

Table 7. Distinguisher results: mean and [min, max] across 3 runs. ρ_{obs} is the observed off-diagonal ratio; $z_{\text{max}}^{\text{lb}}$ is the maximum low-bit z-score across all RNS primes. Main configurations only.

Lib	Coll Def	R^2 mean [range]	Low-bit [range]	ρ_{obs}	$z_{\text{max}}^{\text{lb}}$	$p_{\text{coll}}, p_{\text{rank}}$
SEAL	0 0	-0.750 [-0.752, -0.749]	0.499 [0.498, 0.500]	≈ 0.10	< 3	1.0, 1.0
OpenFHE	0 0	-0.750 [-0.751, -0.749]	0.500 [0.499, 0.500]	≈ 0.05	< 3	1.0, 1.0
HElib	0 0	≈ 0.000 [-0.001, 0.001]	0.500 [0.500, 0.500]	≈ 0.10	< 3	1.0, 1.0
SEAL (stress)	0 0	-0.750 [-0.751, -0.750]	0.500 [0.499, 0.500]	≈ 0.05	< 3	1.0, 1.0

Fig. 1. Distinguisher outputs (collision count, rank deficit, R^2 mean, low-bit mean, and ρ) for run_001 of each library. Dashed reference lines mark the null values: collision = 0, deficit = 0, $R^2 \approx -0.75$ or 0, low-bit = 0.5, and $\rho \approx \rho_{\text{null}}$ (library-specific). All bars/points lie within the null band, consistent with the null hypothesis of no detectable leakage.

Run-to-run stability is confirmed by the narrow metric ranges in Table 7: the R^2 mean for SEAL varied by only 0.003 across three runs. The negative result is consistent across all three libraries and all three runs; three independent key generations per library is a minimal but reproducible baseline.

The Frobenius norm $\|C\|_F \approx \sigma_l^2 \sqrt{n_{\text{cov}}}$ under the null ($N \gg n_{\text{cov}}$; see Section 5.2) confirms that the diagonal of C dominates, as expected. For the three main-library configurations, all ρ_{obs} values fell within the null band from Table 3.

The five distinguisher outputs for run_001 of each library appear in Figure 1. Figure 2 shows the per-prime bias metrics (low-bit mean and excess kurtosis) across all three runs.

7.3 Control Validation

The control experiments show that the distinguishers respond to injected structure and remain silent on clean data (Figure 3). In the **positive** control (one duplicated block), the pipeline detected `collision_count` = 1 and rank deficit = 1,

Fig. 2. Per-prime bias metrics across three runs per library. *Top:* low-bit mean (dashed reference at 0.5). *Bottom:* excess kurtosis (dashed reference at -1.2). Shaded bands show the null 99th-percentile interval from Table 3. All points fall within the band, consistent with the null hypothesis.

Fig. 3. Control validation results (SEAL). **Left:** Positive control: duplicate block injection produces `collision_count` = 1 and rank deficit = 1, as expected. **Middle:** Scaled control: replacing one block with $\mathbf{v}' = \lambda \mathbf{v} \bmod q_l$ yields rank deficit = 1 and zero collisions. **Right:** Fresh control: three independent key generations produce all metrics at their null values, confirming no false alarms. Dashed lines mark the null reference values.

as expected. In the **scaled** control (one block replaced by $\lambda \mathbf{v}_j \bmod q_l$), the collision count remained zero (the scaled block hashes differently), while the rank deficit was 1 and ρ increased. In the **fresh** control (three fully independent key generations), the pipeline reported zero collisions, zero deficit, $R^2 \approx -0.75$, and low-bit mean ≈ 0.50 , with no false alarms. The positive and scaled controls therefore verify detection of exact and linear-structure anomalies, whereas the fresh control bounds false positives under clean sampling. These outcomes support the operational validity of the decision rules used in Section 5. Since these controls were executed on SEAL, they validate detector behavior in that implementation context and motivate analogous control campaigns for OpenFHE and HELIB.

8 Discussion and Limitations

Several limitations deserve explicit mention.

8.1 Methodological Limitations

Sample size. Three independent key generations per library is a minimal baseline within the current study scope. The narrow run-to-run ranges in Table 7 indicate stability, but ten or more generations per library with stricter multiple-testing corrections [20] would strengthen the claim. Null-simulation threshold calibration used 100 draws per configuration; 1,000 or more are recommended for tighter percentile estimates in follow-up work.

Parameter coverage. We tested SEAL with CKKS at $N \in \{4096, 32768\}$, OpenFHE with CKKS at $N = 16384$, and HELib with BGV at $N = 2048$ (cyclotomic index $m_{\text{cyc}} = 4096$, characteristic $p = 3$). These results do not generalize to all parameter choices: varying ring dimension, prime bit-lengths, decomposition base (digit vs. RNS), or rotation key count may produce different distributions.

Scope of tested objects. We consider only evaluation keys. Ciphertexts, public keys, secret keys, and plaintexts are out of scope.

Test sensitivity. As analyzed in Section 5.7, the collision and rank tests have perfect sensitivity to their respective deviation types, and the bias z-score test detects sub-percent biases. However, the covariance and regression tests are calibrated for moderate-to-strong structure and may miss subtle correlations. The regression threshold $R_{\text{max}}^2 > 0.9$ is particularly conservative.

Untested libraries. The pipeline is designed for extension to Lattigo [1] and TFHE [11], but those libraries were not tested in this work.

Future work. A single follow-up campaign should jointly expand run counts, broaden parameter coverage, include non-evaluation-key objects, add controls for OpenFHE and HELib, and test additional ecosystems such as Lattigo and TFHE.

8.2 Implementation Notes

SEAL stores coefficients in NTT form; the positive control confirms that injected structure is detectable in this domain. HELib stores a PRG seed for sk_1 and regenerates coefficients on demand; we dump the regenerated values following the procedure in [15]. The validity of this dump assumes the regenerated coefficients are bit-identical to those used internally during key switching; any divergence in PRG initialization state or polynomial indexing would mean the dumped values are not the actual material being tested. This was verified by comparing regenerated outputs against runtime key-switching on a synthetic test vector. For OpenFHE, coefficients are extracted per RNS prime using the library’s internal polynomial type, `DCRTPoly` (Double-CRT polynomial), which stores each polynomial as its L RNS residues. HELib occasionally generates “thin” rotation keys with fewer than N coefficients; across our three HELib runs, a total of 47 thin blocks were encountered (out of 36,936 blocks across all runs, $\approx 0.13\%$) and were

discarded before analysis. The rank test performs exact Gaussian elimination over \mathbb{Z}_{q_i} using Python arbitrary-precision integers; for HELib ($n_{\text{vec}} = 2,052$ rows, $N = 2,048$ columns) this is computationally expensive, so rows were capped at 500 by uniform random sampling before the rank computation.

9 Conclusion

This work presents GaloisProbe, a practical cryptographic-auditing framework for evaluating whether HE evaluation keys satisfy RLWE-style randomness assumptions in deployed implementations. Using five complementary distinguishers in a key-only setting, together with SEAL-based control validation of detector behavior, we analyze SEAL, OpenFHE, and HELib and test for mask reuse, exact linear dependence, covariance structure, regression dependence, and coefficient bias. Across all tested settings and runs, we observe no detectable deviation from the ideal model.

The primary contribution is methodological: translating proof assumptions into a reproducible distinguisher suite with explicit calibration, power analysis, and control checks that other auditors can reuse. The present findings are an empirical baseline rather than a formal security proof, bounded by the current study scope (three libraries, four parameter settings, and five test families). A natural next step is a broader campaign with more generations, wider parameter coverage, stronger goodness-of-fit and spectral tests, and additional HE ecosystems such as Lattigo and TFHE.

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